

Counterfactual Explanations for Agentic Workflows

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Agentic workflows are structured systems that integrate LLMs and API tools to manage ordered task executions. Because agentic workflows rely on generative systems that do not yield a single bounded decision and instead create structured artifacts with many valid outputs, explainable AI (XAI) techniques developed for isolated models using feature weightings, gradient tracing, or attention maps are insufficient. In this paper, we present an API that makes agentic workflows explainable via counterfactual explanations, which can show how small changes to inputs or plans would alter the outcome and thus help users understand decision boundaries. Our API makes it easy for users to generate counterfactuals that intervene in any part of the workflow. The user interacts with the workflow in two ways, (1) via an interactive interface with which to visually inspect runtime execution data and counterfactuals; (2) via an LLM-based agent, separate from the workflow, that can suggest counterfactuals, summarize code, answer questions about the workflow codebase, and textually describe execution traces and counterfactuals.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Interactive systems and tools**; • **Information systems** → **Language models**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Explainable AI, Large Language Models, Agentic AI, Agentic workflows, Counterfactuals

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) are increasingly incorporated into applications and services to perform tasks in an *agentic* manner—taking an active role or producing a specified outcome to autonomously help users accomplish an overall goal. Developers create *agentic workflows* to effectively integrate LLM agents with non-LLM components. For example, a developer working on an app to help users complete home improvement projects more easily may create an *agentic workflow* that uses an agentic LLM to summarize reviews for different online products; the left side of Figure 1 visualizes the example agentic workflow as a directed graph.

In this paper, we investigate Explainable AI (XAI) for agentic workflows to yield insights for developers to modify the interaction between components, make changes to non-AI components, or better incorporate agentic LLMs. Within agentic workflows, calls to LLMs are structured as prompts, which are sets of instructions, context, and constraints that define clear objectives, approaches, and tools for the LLM to follow. However, LLMs are a “new and difficult design material” [4, 31, 32] due to the nature of interactions between training, fine-tuning, and stochasticity of token generation. As a result, correctly integrating an LLM into an agentic workflow is critical but challenging. If the workflow response is incorrect, undesirable, or harmful, how did each call to LLM and non-LLM components contribute to that response? In which part of the workflow would an intervention be most effective? Traditionally AI explanations may provide human-understandable justifications for a system’s behavior [1, 9] through model feature weightings [14], gradient tracing [22, 24], attention maps [10, 30], and other methods. However, the behavior of the entire workflow is a product of the interaction between LLM and non-LLM components, new approaches are needed to explain agentic workflows [27].

We present an API that can be used in conjunction with other workflow frameworks to help developers understand and modify their agentic workflows by (a) summarizing the workflow and answering questions about individual modules, (b) tracing and visualizing data as it flows through unique workflow runs, and (c) allowing developers to explore how alternative inputs and/or alternative workflow runs may affect outputs. As depicted in Figure 2, the API

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Fig. 1. An example workflow for a product recommendation system. The *Workflow View* shows the initial workflow, where (A1) selecting a module opens (A2) an inspection panel for examining module details and (A3) generating counterfactual runs. The *Counterfactual View* compares the initial execution run against the new counterfactual run, where (B1) highlighted nodes indicate differences caused by the injected counterfactual input, and (B2) a comparison panel displays the changed modules. The (C) Run Lineage visualizes the history of execution runs, where nodes represent runs and edges indicate parent-child relationships formed when a counterfactual run is generated from a prior run. The (D) AI Assistant (orchestrator) is available at the bottom of both views.

creates a facsimile of the developer’s AI workflow, and then aids the developer in exploring it by exposing both a visual and a conversational interface.

2 Background and Related Work

To date, a majority of XAI research has focused on opaque classification and regression models, where explanations help users understand a specific prediction given an input [25]. Other XAI work, moved from explaining individual model predictions to characterizing failures in complex, multi-component systems, where errors compound across pipeline stages in ways single-model metrics cannot capture [20]. Methods include assigning blame to specific components via human computation [19], propagating Shapley values through model sequences to attribute end-to-end behavior to input features [3], and provenance-based debugging tools for multi-step pipelines [13]. Agentic workflows present a distinct challenge given their reliance on generative systems that do not yield a single bounded decision and instead create structured artifacts with many valid outputs. Thus, insights from discriminative ML explainability (e.g., [12]), which targets user needs around justifying decisions within a bounded prediction space, do not directly apply. Generative AI is especially challenging to explain because it is iterative, co-creative, tightly woven into workflows, and must support continuous human steering [27]. A study of software engineers using AI-generated code concluded that explainability should be integrated into surrounding workflows rather than confined to isolated model introspection [27]. XAI challenges are exacerbated in agentic workflows, as different workflow components become more complex with self-refinement and can evolve with richer memory and planning capabilities [23]. Moreover, agentic AI is being deployed in many critical domains with significant real-world impact. XAI for agentic workflow can help fill what Raza et al. [21] call the “Transparency Gap”, that resulted when we moved from static models to agentic AI. Raza et al. [21] further call for agentic systems to be traceable, responsive to stakeholders’ needs, and attentive to the full life cycle of the workflow rather than just static predictions. To this end, they echo earlier calls for human-centered XAI to understand stakeholders’ needs [5] and to attend to the broader ecosystems in which they operate [6].

There are various strategies for explainability of generative and agentic AI, including chain of thought, counterfactuals, which are most relevant to our work and detailed below. Raza et al. [21] provide a survey that adds ReAct-style traces

Fig. 2. System Architecture. Execution data is obtained from registered workflow modules and stored as provenance data. User queries are passed from the Visualizer to the Orchestrator agent, which parses them to detect pertinent actions. Each action is routed to its tool handler which obtains the data required, executes the action, and sends an explanation of the results back to the user.

[33] that incorporate tool calls into CoT that can be verified, retrieval attribution [15], policy logging [2], and others. *Chain-of-thought* (CoT) reasoning [29] generates outputs that first breaks complex tasks into simpler tasks; these “chains” can be interpreted as explanations insofar as they describe an order of sub-tasks to be fulfilled. However, these are self-generated rationales, and are not guaranteed to be faithful to the underlying computation and can even reflect hallucinated justifications [28].

Counterfactual explanations contrast AI behavior against an alternative that did not happen [7, 17]. Counterfactual explanations explain (a) what would happen if conditions were different or if a different choice was made; or (b) what would have had to be true for something else to have happened. In agentic workflows, the counterfactual may initiate with an alternative set of inputs but can also happen through *state injections* where the intermediate state of the workflow is altered to see the effects henceforth. Counterfactual explanations for LLMs can show how small changes to inputs or plans would alter the outcome, helping users understand decision boundaries [16]. However, they can be unreliable if self-generated [18].

Agentic workflows are structured systems that integrate AI agents and API tools to manage ordered task execution. Conceptually, such workflows are often modeled as directed graphs whose nodes represent decision or operation points and whose edges encode control-flow dependencies [34]. The term *provenance* refers to the entities involved in producing data that can be used to assess its quality, reliability, or trustworthiness [8]. In agentic AI systems, this concept extends to a unified provenance graph that traces prompts, model calls, tool use, and outputs, enabling transparent, end-to-end traceability [26]. However, more than traceability of data generated throughout a workflow is needed. Sun et al. [27] conducted a human participant study and conclude that agentic system users seek to understand how outputs change with different prompts, which hypothetical conditions influence artifact generation, and how to steer the overall generation process.

3 An API for Explaining Agentic Workflows

We introduce an API that makes agentic workflows explainable. The API automatically traces data provenance, which can be summarized textually or visualized. Counterfactual state injections can be requested and likewise summarized textually or visually. Figure 2 shows our architecture. Code hooks enable automatic capture of data provenance during workflow execution, which can be manipulated by tools that are instantiated when the user interacts with an AI Assistant or directly via an interactive visualization interface. We provide details about the components below.

3.1 Orchestrator Agent and Tools

The framework automatically provides an interface to the *orchestrator*, which invokes an LLM-based agent (separate from the LLM invocations in the workflow) to interpret user questions and requests as tool calls. Example interactions for each tool can be found in Appendix A.

The *Summarizer Tool* summarizes the workflow at the granularity of a module, a class, a library or the full project by using the local source code and/or drawing upon documentation. Based on the orchestrator agent’s interpretation of the depth of the user query, it may launch multiple sub-agents to summarize specific components. Code summarization is a capability common across LLM coding assistants and our main contributions lie in the subsequent tools.

The *Narrative Tool* lets the user query the system about the execution of their agentic workflow. When the workflow is executed, provenance data—modules and their static data (code, docstring) and execution data (execution order, inputs, outputs)—is collected. The narrative tool queries the provenance data for relevant pieces to ground their explanation of the workflow with regards to the user’s query. Coding assistants do not natively perform this functionality.

The *Counterfactual Tool* supports what-if analyses by re-executing a subgraph of the user’s workflow with modified inputs. Given a user query (e.g., "how would this change if the review score was a 4/5 instead of a 2/5?"), a planning sub-agent identifies the target module, modified input values, and dependent modules. Upon user approval of the plan, each affected module is re-executed in order with later nodes receiving updated inputs. The new executions are then reported to the user and compared to the original run in the visualization. The user can also choose to edit a value directly in the visualization and initiate the same flow at any place in the workflow.

3.2 Interactive Visualization

When the framework is used to analyze agentic workflows, it is also able to generate visualizations of the static arrangements of the modules (see Figure 1). Based on the provenance data as opposed to just static code, the visualization displays the part of the workflow that executed. This means that if a part of the workflow does not execute, e.g. due to conditional branching, it would not show up in the visualization. Users get an overview of the full workflow, where they can get more granular information of individual or clustered modules by selecting them. The visualization allows inputs via both module selections and chat entries. The responses may include textual explanations through the chat window, or an update in the workflow structure/data, or both. Counterfactual induced updates can be compared with the original run using a comparison view that clearly displays the variations. Changes made over multiple re-runs can be tracked using a *Run Lineage* that indicates which runs originated from which base runs.

4 Case Study

To illustrate how our system supports explanation of agentic workflows, we present a case study of a simplified product recommendation workflow that processes customer reviews to recommend newer products to them; this is a very common task in the domain of sales. The example workflow, shown in Figure 1, takes a prior review of a product, identifies features that the reviewer likes or dislikes, and generates recommendations. For example, if a reviewer noted in their product review that an appliance had high energy consumption, the recommendation system would advise users to avoid that product if energy efficiency is an important feature for them. It consists of five modules: `analyze_sentiment` and `generate_recommendations` use LLM calls for their functionality, while the rest use adhoc rule-based functions to pre- or post-process the LLM module inputs and outputs.

User Task. Suppose a user leaves a negative review for a computer mouse complaining about the battery life, and is recommended an alternative mouse with longer battery life. A manager wants to test that the agent instead suggests other upgrades (e.g., a portable charger) if the user’s review is positive.

Conventional Approach. The conventional debugging approach requires developers to: (1) manually modify input values to the workflow or intermediate modules, (2) re-execute the entire workflow, (3) manually transcribe outputs to a spreadsheet for comparison, and (4) repeat this process for each counterfactual scenario.

Code Assistant Approach. We ran GitHub Copilot (1.388.0) within Visual Studio Code (1.106.2) IDE as a baseline surrogate for our orchestrator. GitHub Copilot is a coding assistant that can execute file reads, edits, and execute code. In this case, the “file” was the script associated with the workflow. In our experiments, we were able to force GitHub Copilot to perform the equivalent of a counterfactual through careful prompting to describe what we were trying to

accomplish. This resulted in more burden on the user. It also meant that the entire interaction occurred within the chat window, which can make it difficult to determine what was happening and what was being changed. To achieve the equivalent effects of a counterfactual, the code assistant had to copy all code into a new file to edit it as it could not begin execution in the middle of a workflow script. If multiple interventions are sought, the management of different code files with different combinations becomes unwieldy and information overload would become a concern. Careful instructions were required to avoid assistant misunderstanding—in at least one trial the assistant altered the code to return dummy values.

Our Approach The manager can validate this counterfactual in two ways. First, they can issue a natural-language request in the chat window, (e.g., “validate the recommendation that would be generated if the customer had given a positive review”). The Counterfactual tool would detect the pertinent module to begin the re-run at, an appropriate input for the requested scenario, and present the plan to the manager for approval before executing it. Alternatively, the manager can run the workflow and manually change the value of the review at the desired node in the visualization of the run and trigger a counterfactual run. In both cases, a comparison view is brought up clearly highlighting where the previous and current runs diverged. The manager can continue iterating, and the system will maintain a structured record of all the changes and subsequent runs. The user can toggle between different runs by selecting them from the run lineage graph (see Figure 1 C) in the visualization.

5 Future Work

We identify three areas of future contributions. First is counterfactuals involving the fine-tuning of LLM-based workflow modules. Workflow frameworks such as DSPy [11] can auto-tune LLM-based modules to improve responses according to given metrics or examples. When models change, it can cause unintended downstream effects. Counterfactuals can be generated using earlier checkpoints to determine and report the effect of auto-tuning on the entire workflow, or parts of a workflow.

Second is to support counterfactual execution of workflows that invoke tool side-effects, which occur when a tool makes a permanent change to an external system such as a database. As counterfactual runs are those that do not actually occur, side-effect from counterfactual runs can be detrimental. Currently external tool calls with side-effects can be caught and suppressed. However, side-effects from one module that changes external systems may impact modules downstream that sense the state of external systems. One potential strategy includes extending the API to allow for external systems that are “counterfactual-aware”—they can themselves be executed in counterfactual mode in which changes are temporary and can be rolled back once the counterfactual is complete. Another strategy is to simulate the effects of side-effects by hallucinating how external systems will be changed by external tool calls.

Third, the orchestrator, harnessing a LLM itself, has the potential to learn to synthesize new, complex tools from simpler, existing tools in response to user queries. For example, fuzzing is a process of sweeping through the space of possible inputs to look for failure conditions; it can in part be achieved via sequential counterfactual runs. This could be similar to how current LLM harnesses such as use “skill files” to record discovered interaction patterns.

6 Conclusions

Agentic LLMs enable developers to create increasingly sophisticated applications and services, but also introduce challenges pertaining to unclear decision boundaries. There is a need for XAI solutions that help developers understand their agentic workflows. Our API addresses this need by exposing a way for developers and users to interact with these workflows. It lets users (1) inspect data as it flows through the workflow as a visual graph diagram (2) get rich textual and/or visual explanations for their queries based in both static and execution data, and (3) run counterfactual executions on part or entirety of their workflow with the ability to compare how their proposed changes altered the downstream execution.

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A AI Assistant Interactions

AI Assistant

Summarize the analyze_sentiment module.

Code Summary:
The `analyze_sentiment` module is the first LLM-powered component that transforms preprocessed review data into structured sentiment insights.

Function: `analyze_sentiment(review_stats: str) -> str`

Purpose: Uses LLM to perform sentiment analysis on customer product reviews.

Input: Receives a JSON string containing review statistics from the preprocessing stage, including:

- Cleaned review text
- Sentence count
- Word count
- Exclamation count (sentiment intensity indicator)

LLM Task: Analyzes customer sentiment from the preprocessed review data.

Output: Returns a JSON string containing five fields:

1. `overall_sentiment`: Classification as "positive", "negative", or "mixed"
2. `sentiment_score`: Numerical score from 0.0 to 1.0
3. `likely_to_repurchase`: Boolean indicating repurchase intent
4. `main_complaint`: String describing primary complaint (or null)
5. `main_praise`: String describing primary praise (or null)

Pipeline Role: This module serves as the critical decision point in the pipeline. Its `sentiment_score` output (with 0.6 threshold) determines whether the system branches to:

- **Upsell strategy** (score ≥ 0.6): Recommend premium upgrades
- **Retention strategy** (score < 0.6): Recommend alternatives addressing complaints

The module includes error handling with try-except blocks and is decorated with `@prov_system.register` for provenance tracking.

Ask about the pipeline...

Fig. 3. The *Summarizer Tool* provides a summary of a workflow module, including its function signature, purpose, input, output, and role within the workflow.

• AI Assistant

Walk me through what happened in this execution.

Here's a complete walkthrough of this pipeline execution:

Step 1: load_review
The pipeline started with a customer review: "I'd give this wireless mouse a 2 out of 5. The battery is awful - it only lasts an hour!!" This review was simply loaded and passed through unchanged.

Step 2: Parallel Processing (extract_product_features & preprocess_review)

Two modules processed the review simultaneously:

- **extract_product_features** used regex patterns to extract structured data:
 - Found a rating: 2.0 out of 5
 - No price mentions, product attributes, or comparison words were detected
- **preprocess_review** cleaned the text and gathered statistics:
 - Removed special characters (apostrophes, dashes)
 - Counted 2 sentences, 19 words, and 2 exclamation marks
 - The exclamation marks indicated strong emotional sentiment

Step 3: analyze_sentiment (LLM Call #1)
This module took the preprocessing statistics and analyzed the sentiment using an LLM. Based on the cleaned text and context (2 sentences, 2 exclamations), it determined:

- Overall sentiment: **negative**
- Sentiment score: **0.2** (very low, indicating strong dissatisfaction)
- Likely to repurchase: **false**
- Main complaint: "battery life only lasts an hour"
- No praise was identified

Step 4: generate_recommendation (Orchestrator)
This orchestrator module received both the product features and sentiment analysis. It checked the sentiment score (0.2) and saw it was below 0.6, indicating a dissatisfied customer. Based on this logic, it routed to a retention strategy rather than an upsell strategy.

Final Output:
The system generated a retention-focused message apologizing for the poor battery life and offering to find alternatives with better battery performance. The message was empathetic and solution-oriented, appropriate for a customer who gave a low rating and expressed frustration.

Key Decision Point: The sentiment score of 0.2 was the critical factor that triggered the retention pathway instead of an upsell pathway.

Ask about the pipeline...

Fig. 4. The *Narrative Tool* generates an explanation of a workflow execution, grounded in provenance data, including execution order and intermediate module outputs.

• AI Assistant

How would the recommendation change if the customer had given a positive review instead?

I've modified the review input at the `load_review` node to change it from a negative review to a positive one. The original review gave a 2/5 rating and complained about awful battery life (only lasting an hour). The new review gives a 5/5 rating and praises the excellent battery life (lasting all day). This change will cascade through the entire pipeline: the sentiment analysis will now detect positive sentiment with a higher score and likely repurchase intent, and the final recommendation will shift from an apology with alternatives to a message that thanks the customer and reinforces their positive experience.

Proposed change: Rerun `load_review` with modified inputs: `{'text': "I'd give this wireless mouse a 5 out of 5. The battery is excellent - it lasts all day long!"}`
 The battery is excellent - it lasts all day long!
 This will re-execute 5 node(s) (target + 4 downstream).

Modified inputs:

```
{
  "text": "I'd give this wireless mouse a 5 out of 5. The battery is excellent - it lasts all day long!"
}
```

Type **yes** to run or **no** to cancel.

yes

Rerun complete! Re-executed 5 node(s).

load_review:
 - output: I'd give this wireless mouse a 2 out of 5. The battery is awful - it only lasts an hour!! → **I'd give this wireless mouse a 5 out of 5. The battery is excellent - it lasts all day long!**

extract_product_features:
 - output: `{"price_mentions": [], "rating_mentioned": 2.0, "product_attributes": [], "comparison_words": []}` → `{"price_mentions": [], "rating_mentioned": 5.0, "product_attributes": [], "comparison_words": []}`

preprocess_review:
 - output: `{"cleaned_text": "I'd give this wireless mouse a 2 out of 5. The battery is awful it only lasts an hour!!", "sentence_count": 2, "word_count": 19, "exclamation_count": 2}` → `{"cleaned_text": "I'd give this wireless mouse a 5 out of 5. The battery is excellent it lasts all day long!", "sentence_count": 2, "word_count": 19, "exclamation_count": 1}`

analyze_sentiment:
 - output: `{"overall_sentiment": "negative", "sentiment_score": 0.2, "likely_to_repurchase": false, "main_complaint": "battery life only lasts an hour", "main_praise": null}` → `{"overall_sentiment": "positive", "sentiment_score": 1.0, "likely_to_repurchase": true, "main_complaint": null, "main_praise": "Excellent battery life that lasts all day long!"}`

generate_recommendation:
 - output: We sincerely apologize that the battery life didn't meet your expectations - only lasting an hour is definitely frustrating and not the experience we want for our customers. We'd love to make this right by offering you alternatives with significantly improved battery performance that will better serve your needs. Your satisfaction is our priority, and we're committed to finding a solution that works for you. → **We're thrilled you're loving the exceptional battery life! As a valued customer who appreciates lasting power, you might want to explore our premium accessories and upgraded models that take battery performance to the next level. These solutions are designed for power users who never want to worry about charging again.**

Answer: If the customer had given a positive review instead, the recommendation would change from an apologetic, problem-solving response to a celebratory, upselling approach:

Negative Review (2/5) Recommendation:
 Apologizes for poor battery life, acknowledges the frustration of only 1-hour battery duration, and offers alternatives with better battery performance to make things right.

Positive Review (5/5) Recommendation:
 Celebrates the customer's satisfaction with the excellent all-day battery life and suggests premium accessories and upgraded models designed for power users who want even more advanced battery performance.

The shift is from damage control and retention to customer delight and upselling to higher-tier products.

Ask about the pipeline...

Fig. 5. The *Counterfactual Tool* proposes a plan to rerun the workflow with a modified (counterfactual) input, awaits user approval, then re-executes the affected modules and displays differences between the original and counterfactual runs.